

SHORT NOTES

On Intermolecular Lennard-Jones Potential Energy Parameters for Radon

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Miller¹ estimated the polarisability (α) of the radon atom and used it to calculate the intermolecular force constants ϵ/k (k being the Boltzmann factor) and σ of the Lennard-Jones (L. J.) potential energy function, namely,

$$u(r) = 4 \epsilon \left\{ \left(\frac{\sigma}{r} \right)^{12} - \left(\frac{\sigma}{r} \right)^6 \right\}$$

[where $u(r)$ = potential energy at the distance of separation, r ; σ = distance of closest approach; ϵ = maximum energy of attraction between the two molecules which occurs at $r = 2^{1/6}\sigma$] for two radon molecules. He has shown that the values $\epsilon/k = 484^\circ \text{K}$ and $\sigma = 4.48 \text{ \AA}$, obtained by Srivastava and Saxena² from diffusion coefficient and molecular weight data, are too high. It is the purpose of this note to calculate ϵ/k and σ of the L.J. potential for the radon molecule by quite a different procedure in order to check these controversial results.

Calculation of ϵ/k .—It seems now fully established³ that for a group of similar substances, e.g., the frozen inert gases of the zero-group of the Periodic Table, the ratios U_0/T_m and $-U_0/T_b$ are approximately constant, U_0 being the latent heat of sublimation at 0°K and T_m and T_b , the absolute melting and boiling points of the substance concerned. For the solid inert gases, $-U_0/T_m$ and $-U_0/T_b$ are respectively equal to 24 and 23 approximately. Since radon is a member of this family, it is expected to behave similarly. So from the principle of correspondence one has for radon,

$$-U_0/T_m \approx 24 \text{ and } -U_0/T_b \approx 23.$$

Taking T_m as 202°K and T_b as 211°K for radon, these relations give $-U_0 = 4848$ cal. and 4853 cal. respectively. Hence one can confidently take the latent heat of sublimation of solid radon at 0°K to be very nearly equal to 4850 cal.

Now for molecules obeying L.J. 12-6 potential, the energy of sublimation at 0°K is related to ϵ/k by the expression:

$$-U_0 = 17.13 \epsilon/k$$

1. Miller, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1960, **64**, 163.

2. *Physica*, 1956, **22**, 253.

3. Gopal, *this Journal*, 1953, **30**, 55; *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1956, **278**, 42; **281**, 217; **279**, 220.

which gives on substituting 4850 for $-U_0$, $\epsilon/k=283^\circ\text{K}$. This value compares very well with 290°K , estimated by Miller⁴, but differs widely from that of Srivastava and Saxena⁵ who found $\epsilon/k=484^\circ\text{K}$.

Calculation of σ .—Brandt⁵ has suggested a modified form of Slater-Kirkwood (S.K.) formula relating polarisability, α , and the dispersion energy, $\zeta_{s.k.}$ (i.e. potential energy arising out of rapid, periodic nuclei-electrons displacement relative to one another) between two identical spherical molecules. The original Slater-Kirkwood expression⁶ for dispersion or attraction energy is

$$\zeta_{s.k.} \times r^6 = -\frac{3}{4} a_0^3 e^4 (N \alpha^3)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where a_0 is the Bohr's radius, e , the electronic charge, and N , the number of electrons in the molecular valency shell (which for radon will be 8). This equation can be simplified⁵ to

$$\zeta_{s.k.} \times r^6 = -12.58 \times 10^{-60} (N \alpha^3)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

From the knowledge of N and α for any particular molecule, one can calculate the value of σ by substituting for $\zeta_{s.k.} \times r^6$, the L.J dispersion energy term $4\epsilon\sigma^6$ in eq.(2). It is well known that the L.J dispersion or attraction energy term, $\zeta_{L.J.} \times r^6 = 4\epsilon\sigma^6$ for noble gas atoms increases faster with the atomic number than that predicted by S. K. theory⁷. Brandt⁵ has therefore improved upon the S. K. expression (2) and has suggested

$$\zeta \times r^6 = -B(N \alpha^3)^\beta \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

in place of eq.(2). The values of constants B and β , evaluated graphically by Brandt⁵, are $B=11.1 \times 10^{-60}$ and $\beta=0.62$. Now substituting for B , β , and N in eq.(3) and equating it to $4\epsilon\sigma^6$, we get

$$4\epsilon\sigma^6 = 11.1 \times 10^{-60} (8 \alpha^3)^\beta \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

According to Miller⁴, the polarisability (α) for the radon molecule is $4.5 \text{ \AA}^3$ or $5.86 \text{ \AA}^3$. On substituting the values of α and ϵ [i.e. $(\epsilon/k) \times k$] in eq. (4), the calculations give $\sigma=4.02 \text{ \AA}$ or $4.36 \text{ \AA}$, depending on whether $\alpha=4.50 \text{ \AA}^3$ or $\alpha=5.86 \text{ \AA}^3$ is used. The former value of $\sigma=4.02 \text{ \AA}$ is inadmissible since it is too low (σ for xenon is $4.02 \text{ \AA}$), but the latter is acceptable and it also agrees with that of Miller ($\sigma=4.34 \text{ \AA}$)

It may be noted with interest that this communication gives the latent heat of sublimation of radon (4850 cal. per g. atom) which does not appear to be available in the literature.

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4. Gopal, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, 53, 406.

5. Brandt, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1955, 24, 501.

6. Slater and Kirkwood, *Phys. Rev.*, 1931, 37, 682.

7. Buckingham, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1937, 160A, 94; Rawlinson, *Quart. Rev.*, 1954, 8, 168.